

Convolutional Neural Networks and Transformers based Techniques for Underwater Marine Debris Classification: A Comparative Study

Bushra Jalil, *Member, IEEE*, Luca Maggiani, *Member, IEEE*, and Luca Valcarengi, *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract

Marine debris poses a substantial threat to ecosystems and their inhabitants, representing a worldwide issue. It is crucial to understand the nature and extent of this environmental issue, given its widespread distribution and diverse nature. In recent years, aerial and underwater imaging has been extensively employed to monitor these debris. The classification of marine debris facilitates the identification of the specific types involved and is crucial for implementing preventive measures. Nevertheless, monitoring demands substantial human effort, indicating the need for automated and cost-effective methodologies. In this context, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool for identifying underwater marine debris, offering several advantages over conventional monitoring processes such as manual visual surveys conducted by divers or the use of remotely operated vehicles. We evaluated deep architectures through transfer learning, utilizing knowledge derived from the ImageNet dataset and applying it to the smaller dataset, considering the limited availability of underwater marine data. While prior literature exclusively focused on CNN-based architectures in their comparative study, this paper additionally incorporates state-of-the-art attention-based deep architectures for classifying underwater marine debris. We utilized multiple training schemes for classifying marine debris, employing a dataset sourced from the database of The Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), which comprises of a library of deep-sea images. The attention-based Swin architecture demonstrated the highest accuracy at 93.08% with relatively higher parameter count, followed by DenseNet121 with an accuracy of 90.99%. MobileNetV2, with the fewest parameters (2.26M), achieved an accuracy of 84.91%. The comparative analysis in this study indicates that transformer-based models exhibited relatively higher accuracies compared to CNNs. However, the selection between CNNs and transformer-based architectures depends on multiple factors such as data availability, computational resources and marine environment.

Index Terms

Bushra Jalil is with TeCIP institute of Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy e-mail: (bushra.jalil@santannapisa.it).

Luca Valcarengi is with TeCIP institute of Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna, Pisa, Italy e-mail: (luca.valcarengi@santannapisa.it).

Luca Maggiani is with Sma-rtly Italia s.r.l, Italy e-mail: (luca.maggiani@sma-rtly.com).

Manuscript received Mar 3rd, 2024; revised July, 2024.

Fig. 1: Sample of raw images of each class sourced from JAMSTEC-library of Deep-Sea images [16].

Under water marine debris, image classification, deep learning, convolutional neural networks, vision transformer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Marine debris, characterized as human-made material entering marine and coastal environments including plastics, metals, glass *etc.* through various sources, is considered a major threat to the health of oceans, their inhabitants, and humans. The widespread distribution and diverse nature of this debris are crucial aspects for understanding the nature and extent of this environmental issue. These materials, ranging from plastics, metals, glass, fishing gear, and other debris, present distinctive challenges when submerged beneath the surface of the ocean due to their diverse nature, shapes, and sizes. Therefore, continuous monitoring of densely polluted regions is extremely important not only to highlight the areas where interventions are most needed but also to develop effective solutions to reduce the severe impacts on marine ecosystems. Furthermore, classifying debris by the type of their material and other characteristics also provides information related to the sources and their distribution. Madricardo et al. provided a comprehensive overview of methods designed to address the challenges of seafloor pollution [1]. They addressed various aspects, including monitoring of macro debris on the seafloor, the identification of potential accumulation and seafloor debris management. Traditionally, underwater marine debris classification is performed through visual inspection, where sea divers or remotely operated vehicles visually inspect the underwater environments and identify objects based on their physical characteristics. However, monitoring sea debris by visual inspection under the sea is a time-consuming, labor-intensive, and expensive process, thus limiting the availability of reliable data for classification. In certain situations, this process becomes extremely challenging due to the diverse nature of the marine environment. To overcome these issues, combining data from different sources, such as visual inspection and remote sensing, can provide a more comprehensive and accurate outcome.

With recent advancements, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a powerful tool for underwater marine debris classification, offering several advantages over manual visual inspection. Most importantly, AI based algorithms can also integrate with autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) to enable real-time monitoring and classification. AI based methods can analyze large datasets of underwater images acquired during the monitoring process and provide

a more efficient, accurate, and cost-effective classification of marine debris distribution. In general, computer vision based machine learning and deep learning methods represent two distinct approaches of AI-based classification. The former method primarily relies on manual domain-specific feature extraction. These features are derived from color histograms, textures, and shape characteristics of images. Such methods significantly depend on an efficient manual feature extraction, which is a challenging task given the diverse nature of the underwater environment. In contrary to that, deep learning techniques offer a more automated and adaptable classification for complex underwater marine environment. Deep learning algorithms present end-to-end learning, where models automatically learn complex, relevant features from raw data and leads to more robust and generalized models that perform equally well on unseen data.

During the last few years, aerial and underwater imaging is extensively employed to monitor objects located at the surface of the sea. However, monitoring of marine debris requires significant human effort, highlighting the necessity for automated and cost-effective methods to classify objects both on the surface and underwater at the seabed. In this context, Marin et al. compared the performance of deep convolutional architectures using real underwater marine debris dataset [3]. They investigated multiple training schemes and compared the performance of conventional machine learning classifiers with neural networks for the classification of marine debris. Similarly, Paula et al. conducted a bibliographic survey on techniques and sensors deployed for marine debris detection [4]. They highlighted that most of the studies utilize satellite platforms and remote sensing for this task and focus particularly on the detection of plastic waste. Sanjai et al. recently presented their findings in classifying underwater marine plastics utilizing two variants of Inception architectures, Inception-ResNetV2, and InceptionV3 [5]. These models were trained on google based underwater plastic waste with pretrained weights. Kylili et al. employed CNNs, using VGG16 architecture to automatically classify floating plastic debris in images [6]. Additionally, they classify different types of plastic debris found at the shoreline and in deep sea. Similarly, Hidaka *et al.* applied semantic segmentation to detect marine debris, emphasizing that patterns with limited features in the training data may diminish segmentation performance [7].

In addition to these approaches, it is observed that during the last few years, Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) and drones are employed for the monitoring and marine data collection purposes. Martin et al. presented a method for marine debris recognition on beaches using images acquired through UAVs, using machine learning classifiers to detect beach debris from orthomosaics [8]. Similarly, Papakonstantinou et al. integrated drone technology with machine learning to create density maps to monitor objects on beaches and nearshore areas [9]. Gonçalves et al. explored machine learning methods for automating detection of debris using data acquired from UAVs, employing machine learning classifier and pixel-by-pixel classification technique [10]. While numerous techniques exist for detecting objects from the surface of the sea, many of which utilize data acquired through cameras mounted on drones/UAVs, the extension of these methods to the underwater domain is an area of ongoing exploration and development. Fulton et al. evaluated four distinct neural network architectures for the detection of plastic debris in realistic underwater environments [11]. The models were specifically trained to identify three classes in underwater environment. Musić et al. investigated more advanced architectures ResNet and VGG16, using YOLO networks for the detection of underwater marine debris [12]. They trained these models using Google based images and

Fig. 2: Schematic illustration of CNNs based classification pipeline.

performed augmentation to increase the dataset. They trained these models on hybrid images, where images were constructed by putting artificial objects into the real underwater background.

Similarly, Sánchez-Ferrer et al. extended their initial research in introducing CleanSea dataset, where performance and limitations were investigated with synthetic data, incorporated in real underwater scenario [13]. They further explored detection algorithms using mask region-based CNNs for automatic marine debris location and classification in the context of limited data availability [13]. Politikos et al. introduced an object detection approach to automatically identify seafloor marine debris in a real-world environment using a Region-based convolutional neural network [14]. The images were acquired through a towed underwater camera for the training and testing purposes. Recently, Corrigan et al. applied instance segmentation methodologies (YOLOACT and the Mask R-CNN models) using TrashCAN dataset for training purpose, using pre-trained model weights trained using COCO [15]. More recently, Jalil et al. applied machine learning classifiers to predict marine debris located under the sea [16].

While various methods have been developed to detect marine debris from the sea surface, the brief literature review suggests that the application of state-of-the-art deep learning models for underwater marine debris is still in its early stages. Therefore, additional study is essential, particularly considering the limited availability of underwater marine data and its impact on the performance of deep architectures. In response to these considerations, this work explores state-of-the-art approaches, ranging from CNNs to attention-based techniques. The main contribution of this work is to investigate CNNs and transformer-based architectures, assessing their performance by comparing them using evaluation metrics outlined in the upcoming section, specifically when trained on a real underwater marine debris dataset. The remaining structure of the paper is outlined as follows: Section 2 introduces the dataset used for the experiments and provides an overview of deep learning-based image classification methods. Detailed explanation of convolutional neural networks and transformers based deep architectures is also given. Section 3 presents the details of experimental design and performance metrics. In section 4, we present the performance of models on underwater marine debris classification along with the detail comparative analysis of CNNs and transformer based architectures. Section 5 summarizes the key findings of the paper and outlines potential directions for future research.

Class	Images	Training set	Test set
Glass	178	143	35
Metal	497	398	99
Plastic	700	560	140
Rubber	211	169	42
Other	390	312	78
No Trash	419	336	83
Total	2395	1918	477

TABLE I: Class-wise data distribution [3].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The dataset utilized in this study contains a single object within each image. Consequently, deep learning architectures designed for image classification tasks were chosen for the comparative study. The selection of deep architectures is based on the well-established design principles of these models and their proven performance on ImageNet dataset. This section explores an overview of all the deep architectures used as feature extractors and further provides the details of dataset utilized for training and testing purposes.

A. Dataset

The dataset used in this work is derived from the database of *The Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC)* [16], supplemented with Google Images, provided by the authors of [1]. The class-wise distribution of data is given in Table I. Each image was visually inspected prior to being added to the dataset and all the provided images were manually labelled and validated by the authors of [1]. The dataset comprises a total of 2,395 images belonging to six classes: *Glass*, *Metal*, *Plastic*, *Rubber*, *Other*, and *No trash*. To ensure a balanced distribution of classes between the training and test sets, the dataset for each class is divided for training and testing purposes. Therefore, 80% of the images were used for training, while the remaining 20% within each class were allocated for evaluating the performance of each model. Further among the 80% of the training set (1,918 images), 20% were utilized for validation purposes during model training. Fig. 1 illustrates the sample of raw images of each class sourced from JAMSTEC-library of deep sea images. This work compare the performance of CNNs and transformer based architectures as a feature extractor to classify underwater marine debris in real complex environment. For feature extraction, data normalization is performed as it directly influences the performance of the predictive model where the data values of the features differ significantly. The dataset used in this work differs significantly from the data the models were trained on. This difference in the distribution of the data can affect the performance of the pretrained models, therefore data normalization is performed to ensure stable training process. The preprocessing steps vary across different architectures, based on their specific requirement. In this work, all the images are pre processed using the corresponding *preprocess_input* function from the *tf.keras.applications* module before undergoing the training step on respective deep architecture. Specifically, for VGG19 and ResNet50 models, images are converted from RGB to BGR format, and each color channel is zero-centered relative to the

unscaled ImageNet data. In the case of InceptionV3, Inception-ResNetV2, MobileNetV2, NasNet, and EfficientNet architectures, pixel values of input images are scaled between -1 and 1. For DenseNet121, pixel values are scaled between 0 and 1, with each color channel subsequently normalized with respect to the ImageNet data. Similarly, for ViT, DeiT, and Swin transformer architectures, all pixel values are scaled between 0 and 1.

B. Convolutional Neural Networks based image classification

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are primarily designed for tasks related to image classification, object detection and segmentation. The main architecture of CNNs as shown in Fig. 2, consists of a sequence of convolutional and pooling layers to extract distinctive features of objects regardless of their size and position, promoting spatial in-variance. These networks are trained in a supervised manner using back-propagation and gradient descent-based optimization. The key components and concepts related to CNNs include: *i) Convolutional layers*: Convolution applies multiple filters of different kernels to the input image, sliding across to generate feature maps, while the trainable weights of the filters are adjusted during back-propagation process. Filters are typically arranged in layers, and with each successive layer, the network learns more complex features as data passes through it. The obtained feature vector consists of optimal points representing information (e.g., shape or texture) related to the objects present in the images. The complete feature maps are obtained by using several different kernels. Mathematically, the feature value at location (i, j) in the k -th feature map of l -th layer, $z_{i,j,k}^l$, is calculated by [18]:

$$z_{i,j,k}^l = w_k^{lT} x_{i,j}^l + b_k^l \quad (1)$$

where w_k^l and b_k^l are the weight vector and bias term of the k -th filter of the l -th layer respectively, and $x_{i,j}^l$ is the input patch centered at location (i, j) of the l -th layer [18]. *ii) Activation function*: Non-linear functions e.g., ReLU applied during the training process, enable the network to learn relationship among the complex features and patterns. The activation value $a_{i,j,k}^l$ of convolutional feature $z_{i,j,k}^l$ can be computed as [18]:

$$a_{i,j,k}^l = a(z_{i,j,k}^l) \quad (2)$$

iii) Pooling or sub sampling layers: Pooling layers in CNNs reduces the size of the feature maps by down sampling (using operations like max pooling or average pooling) while preserving the essential information. The pooling layers aggregate information within feature map a_k by replacing local pooling regions $R_{i,j}$ in a_k with the maximum element from $R_{i,j}$ in the case of max pooling, and with arithmetic mean of elements in $R_{i,j}$ in the case of average pooling and global average pooling averages all values in a_k . *iv) Flatten layer*: Flatten layer transform a multidimensional feature map into a one-dimensional vector before passing to fully connected layers. *v) Fully connected (FC) dense layers*: FC layers are crucial for tasks related to classification, takes feature map as an input from previous layers.

In FC layers, each neuron in the current layer is connected to every neuron in the previous layer such as $O_i = \sigma(\sum_j w_{i,j} \cdot I_j + b_i)$, where I_j is the j^{th} input to the layer. $w_{i,j}$ is the weight connecting the j^{th} input to i^{th} neuron. b_i is the bias term for the i^{th} neuron and σ denote the activation function (ReLU) [18]. The final softmax-based prediction is the resulting class of the input image, achieved by transforming the raw scores into probabilities using the mathematical expression below. The class with the highest probability is typically selected

Model	Year	Parameters	Vector Size	Characteristics/Limitations
VGG19	2014	20,02M	512	Deep CNN model, large number of parameters, complex, vanishing gradients
InceptionV3	2015	21,80M	2048	Improved accuracy through inception modules (wider network), complex and computationally expensive
ResNet50	2015	23,59M	2048	Adressed vanishing gradients through residual connections
Inception-ResNetV2	2016	54,34M	1536	Combined Inception architecture with residual connections
DenseNet121	2017	7,04M	1024	Dense connectivity patterns, facilitating feature reuse across layers
Xception	2017	20,86M	2048	Combined Inception and ResNet, performed depth-wise separable convolution
MobileNetV2	2018	2,26M	1280	Lightweight model, designed for resource-constrained devices
NasNet (Mobile)	2018	4,27M	1056	Based on AutoML concept (search algorithm to find optimal architecture)
EfficientNet B0	2019	4,05M	1280	Compound scaling, high accuracy while being computationally efficient
ViT	2020	85,80M	768	Transformer architecture, based on self attention, trained on huge data
DeiT	2020	5,53M	192	Introduced distillation in transformer, addressed huge training data requirement of transformers
Swin	2021	27,52M	768	Introduced featuring a hierarchical structure in transformers

TABLE II: Summary of CNNs and transformer based deep architectures along with their parameters, feature vector size and characteristics

as the predicted class. $Softmax(z)_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_j e^{z_j}}$, where $Softmax(z)_i$ is the probability assigned to class i , e^{z_i} represents the logit of class i and the denominator is the sum of the exponential of all logit values across classes, ensuring that the probabilities sum up to 1, making it a valid probability distribution [18].

In the next sections, we present a brief overview of the CNN architectures utilized as a feature extractor marine debris classification.

1) *VGG19*: VGGNet, proposed by Karen Simonyan and Andrew Zisserman in 2014, is a standard deep CNN architecture with multiple layers [19]. VGGNet enhances the performance of preceding models by replacing larger filters with sequences of smaller filters (3×3) and deeper networks with more non-linearities (a stack of three 3×3 conv (stride 1) layers has the same effective receptive field as one 7×7 conv layer). VGG19 supports 19 trainable layers with uniform components in a feed forward manner (16 convolution layers, 3 fully connected layers, 5 maxpool layers, and 1 softmax layer). Although VGGNets improved the performance of CNN-based models with high generalization ability, but the large number of trainable parameters leads VGGNets to suffer from exploding gradients issues.

2) *InceptionV3*: The Inception architecture, developed by Szegedy et al. in 2015 [20], is based on the idea of using filters of varying kernel sizes at the same level (in parallel) to capture information simultaneously, making the network wider rather than deeper. There is a significant variation in the location of information inside the image, and choosing the right kernel size for the convolutional operation is a challenging task. A larger kernel is preferred

for information that is distributed more globally, while a smaller kernel captures finer details. The V3 version of the Inception models introduced two additional ideas: i) factorization idea, replacing a 5×5 filter (25) with two 3×3 filters (9+9), thereby reducing the number of parameters without decreasing network efficiency; and ii) an auxiliary classifier that calculates the loss through an auxiliary classifier and later adds it to the main loss, preventing the vanishing gradient problem during training.

3) *ResNet50*: The intuition behind *deeper, the better* holds true for convolutional neural networks, as deeper networks exhibit high generalization ability. However, the performance tends to degrade after a certain depth due to the vanishing gradient phenomenon. ResNet50, a CNNs based architecture proposed by He et al. in 2015 [21], addressed this degradation in training accuracy (due to vanishing gradients) by introducing skip connections where data flows through and around the layers. The skip connection connects activations of a layer to subsequent layers by skipping some intermediate layers, creating a residual block. ResNet50 is composed of 48 convolutional layers, one MaxPool layer, and one average pool layer. ResNet50 employs a bottleneck design for its building blocks. A bottleneck residual block uses 1×1 convolutions to reduce the number of parameters, thus accelerating the training process.

4) *Inception-ResNetV2*: Inception-ResNet, proposed by Szegedy et al. in 2016 [22], combines the well-performing Inception architecture with the residual framework to reduce the complexity of Inception models. The basic building block of Inception-ResNet-V2 is called the Residual Inception block, and in this block, a 1×1 convolution filter with an activation function is employed after each block to increase the filter bank dimensionality before addition, matching the input depth. Inception-ResNet-V2 features 164 trainable layers with an input image size of 299×299 . With the use of residual connections, this architecture also prevents the performance degradation that occurs in deeper networks due to vanishing gradients, as explained before.

5) *Xception*: Xception, which stands for an extreme version of Inception and was proposed by François Chollet in 2017 [23], is a network architecture that focuses on minimizing connections with fewer trainable parameters compared to earlier versions of Inception. The Xception architecture is primarily based on the utilization of modified depthwise separable convolution and skip connections between convolution blocks. Typically in deep learning, separable convolution performs a spatial convolution independently over each channel of an input, followed by pointwise convolution (1×1 conv). Xception introduced a modified version of separable convolution by reversing the order of operations. The modified depthwise separable convolution involves pointwise convolution followed by depthwise/channelwise convolution. This modification is motivated by the inception module in Inception-v3, where 1×1 convolution is performed before $n \times n$ spatial convolutions. The idea of using separable convolution leads Xception to a reduction in the number of parameters while enhancing the performance of CNNs.

6) *DenseNet121*: DenseNets, which stands for Densely Connected Convolutional Networks and was proposed by Huang et al. in 2017 [24], signify a significant advancement in deep convolutional networks by addressing the issue of vanishing gradients as networks become deeper. Huang et al. addressed the vanishing gradients issue by introducing a dense connectivity pattern, where every layer inside a dense block is directly connected to subsequent layers. Each layer receives feature-maps from preceding layers as an input and by connecting layers in this manner. The DenseNet121 architecture consists of four dense blocks, with each block comprising 6, 12, 24, and 16 smaller

building blocks, respectively. In each dense block, a 1×1 convolution layer reduces the number of input features for computational efficiency. Transition layers following dense blocks further reduce the depth and spatial size of the input volume. The network is advantageous in terms of strengthening feature propagation while maintaining parameter efficiency.

7) *MobileNetV2*: MobileNets, proposed by Mark Sandler et al. in 2018 [25], share a common approach with previously proposed models such as Xception and Inception, relying on the use of separable convolutions as a fundamental building block. In contrast to previous models, where the primary focus is on achieving high precision, MobileNets, with a depth of 53 layers, emphasize finding a balance between model compression and accuracy. In this context, *small* indicates that the number of parameters is low considering the level of accuracy achieved, requiring comparatively less memory. Additionally, the number of Floating-point Operations (FLOPS) is fewer for the level of accuracy attained, meaning the model requires a modest amount of computational resources to make an inference. MobileNets are still considered the most parameter-efficient models based on CNNs for the level of accuracy they achieve.

8) *NASNet(Mobile)*: The Neural Architecture Search Network (NASNet), proposed by Zoph et al. in 2017 [26], is based on the Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) concept and is specifically designed to find the best architecture within a predefined search space, treating it as a reinforcement learning problem. NASNet aimed to search for the best combination of parameters within the given search space, including filter sizes, channels, strides, number of layers *etc.* In the NASNet architecture, a controller neural network generates a candidate architecture, which is then evaluated based on its performance on a given dataset, feedback on the performance of the candidate architecture is then used to update the parameters of controller, generating architectures that achieve better results in terms of performance metrics, model size, and complexity. In NASNet, architectural blocks, namely normal and reduction cells, are arranged in different configurations to generate further variations *e.g.*, NASNet(Mobile) exhibited smaller changes in terms of architecture but shared a parameter count comparable to MobileNet with improved accuracy. Hence, the NASNet(Mobile) model is also a compact and efficient version of NASNet specifically developed for devices with constrained computational capabilities.

9) *EfficientNet(B0)*: In a deeper CNN architecture, increasing the number of layers enhances performance, but networks often encounter vanishing gradient issues. Though the residual framework (skip connection) has addressed this issue to some extent, but significant number of layers result in a considerable rise in computational demands. EfficientNet, introduced by Mingxing Tan et al. in 2019 [27], addresses these challenges by uniformly scaling the dimensions of depth, width (increasing the number of channels or feature maps), and resolution (image height and width) in a more systematic manner, termed as compound scaling. With this concept, EfficientNet achieved higher efficiency by increasing the dimensions (width, depth, and resolution) of the model without compromising accuracy. This strategy enables the model to establish an ideal balance between performance and efficiency, allowing it to adapt to resource-constrained devices. The baseline model, EfficientNetB0, is designed through Neural Architecture Search (NAS), an automated approach for discovering optimal neural network architectures.

We have presented a concise overview of CNN-based deep architectures investigated in this study. In the subsequent section, we will introduce transformer-based deep architectures. Additionally, Table II summarizes the

Fig. 3: Transformer architecture: Image is divided into fixed-size patches, linearly embed each patch, incorporate position embeddings, and feed the resulting sequence of vectors into a conventional Transformer encoder. For classification, we adopt the standard approach of appending an additional learnable classification token to the sequence. The illustration of the transformer encoder was inspired by Vaswani et al. [28]

parameters, feature vector size, and characteristics of the convolutional neural networks and transformer-based models explored in this work. The characteristics in the table represent the distinct attributes and performance traits of each examined model.

C. Transformer based image classification

Transformers, a deep learning model introduced in 2017 [28], were originally designed for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks such as Google translate, demonstrating remarkable success in capturing long-range dependencies in sequential data. The success of transformers in NLP, particularly with models like Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) and Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT), inspired researchers to explore the possibility of applying the transformer model to computer vision tasks. However, images present unique challenges compared to the sequential data, including higher dimensionality, complex spatial relationships, and the presence of noise and redundant information. Khan et al. presented a comprehensive overview of transformer models developed for computer vision applications [29]. After several explorations, Vision Transformers (ViTs) emerged as the first successful approach to adapting transformer architectures for any computer vision task.

1) *ViT*: The ViT, introduced in 2020 as a novel transformer-based approach for computer vision tasks, outperformed state-of-the-art convolutional networks in multiple benchmarks after being pre-trained on a large dataset [30]. Transformer-based architectures are mainly designed on the self-attention mechanism and rely on capturing large-range dependencies within the image. Self-attention allows them to capture global relationships between pixels or regions across the entire image. The schematic illustration of the ViT framework is provided in Fig. 3. The operation of Vision Transformers (ViTs) can be summarized in the following steps: *i*) In ViT, a 2D image $X \in \mathbb{R}^{h \times w \times c}$ is reshaped into a sequence of patches, $X_p = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$, where X_p is the patch representation of the image.

Each patch is then transformed into a vector representation, with x_i representing the i^{th} patch vector/token [30]. *ii)* Linear projection, $X_p = w_p \cdot x_p + b_p$, is applied to reduce the dimensionality of the patches, making computations more efficient and robust by eliminating irrelevant variations and noises to focus more on essential features. *iii)* Similar to the class token of BERT, a learnable embedding is applied to the sequence of patches, serving as the image representation.

In addition, 1D position embeddings are added to the patches to retain positional information, as transformers are position-independent. *iv)* In the transformer block, self-attention captures dependencies between the patches, enabling the model to consider the global context. Given a sequence of items x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n , the self-attention mechanism computes a new representation y_i for each element x_i by considering all elements in the sequence. The mathematical formulation of position embeddings is given in [30]. *v)* Following the self-attention layer, the output is passed through a feedforward network to capture complex non-linear relationships within the patches. Layer normalization is applied to the output of each sub-layer (attention and feedforward) to stabilize the training process. Additionally, residual connections prevent vanishing gradients during the training process. *vi)* The final layer of the transformer encoder is a classification head that maps the output of the transformer into the desired output. ViT is typically pre-trained on large datasets, transfer learning and fine-tuning are then performed for downstream tasks with smaller datasets. These steps illustrate how ViTs process input images and utilize transformer architecture for computer vision applications. In general, pre-training on large datasets is common for transformer based architectures, followed by fine-tuning on smaller datasets for specific applications.

2) *DeiT*: ViTs have demonstrated excellent performance on image classification tasks, surpassing state-of-the-art convolutional architectures in terms of accuracy. However, despite their success, the availability of large training datasets (hundreds of millions of images) and substantial computational resources limits their adoption. ViTs may not generalize well when trained on insufficient data [30], as training on large datasets enables them to learn diverse and representative features. DEiT, Data-efficient Image Transformer, proposed in 2021 [31], was an attempt to address the challenges related to data efficiency and knowledge transfer. DEiT incorporates a distillation approach that involves transferring knowledge from a larger teacher model to a smaller student model. A distinctive feature of DEiT is the use of cross-attention for distillation. The student model learns from the attention maps of the teacher model, facilitating efficient knowledge transfer and contributing to the overall efficiency of the model on specific downstream tasks.

3) *Swin Transformer*: The Swin transformer, a vision transformer using shifted windows, was proposed by Liu et al. in 2022 [32]. It introduces a novel hierarchical approach that processes images in a multi-level, shifted-window manner, enabling the model to efficiently capture information across different scales. Instead of processing the entire image simultaneously, the Swin transformer utilizes a shifted-windows mechanism. This approach allows the model to focus on both local and global context, enhancing its ability to detect objects of varying sizes within an image. Similar to other transformer architectures, the Swin transformer employs self-attention mechanisms, enabling it to effectively capture long-range dependencies in the input data.

In this section, we provided concise summaries of all CNNs and transformer-based deep architectures. Table II further summarizes the characteristics of all architecture discussed in this section. We also presented multiple

parameters of these architectures in the table. The following section outlines the experimental design for this study and the performance of deep architectures on under water marine debris dataset.

III. EXPERIMENTS

The effective training of a deep learning model depends on the availability of substantial labelled data. However, obtaining a large dataset, particularly for underwater marine debris, is challenging due to the complexities of the ocean environment. To address the constraint of a small dataset, transfer learning has emerged as a powerful approach, proving particularly advantageous when limited data is available for a given task. In the present work, we evaluated deep architectures as explained in the preceding section, using transfer learning, leveraging knowledge acquired from the ImageNet dataset [33] and applying it to the smaller available dataset of underwater debris.

A. Experimental Setup

For the implementation, we used Python 3.9.16, employing the TensorFlow 2.6.0 machine learning framework and its Tensorflow.Keras API. All models were trained using the Adam optimizer with learning rate of $lr = 10^{-4}$, $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$ and $\epsilon = 10^{-7}$. We maintained a *batch size* of 16 to accommodate the larger models within the available resources. To augment the dataset, we employed various techniques, including random rotations (*rotation_range* = 45), shearing (*shear_range* = 0.2), brightness (*brightness_range* = (0.2, 1), zooming (*zoom_range* = 0.2), height shift (*height_shift_range* = [-50, 50]) and horizontal flipping (*horizontal_flip* = *True*), during the training process. We also used fill mode *wrap* for handling image augmentation.

Based on the initial empirical evaluation, all CNN-based models were trained for 100 epochs using heuristic approach, while transformer based architectures were trained for 30 epochs. Transformer based architectures were trained for fewer epochs due to faster convergence of these models on the given dataset. It is worth mentioning that the results reported in this work indicate the highest accuracy achieved by each respective model, regardless of the epoch at which the accuracy was achieved. During the training process of CNN models with a combined scheme of fixed feature extraction and fine-tuning, we initially trained only the classifier on top while keeping the deep CNN layers frozen for the first 25 epochs. Following this, over the subsequent 75 epochs, fine-tuning was applied to both the weights of the deep CNN and the classifier. The weights of all the models were initialized with the ImageNet dataset (using transfer learning) [33], pretrained for 1000 classes on 1.2 million images, compared to the dataset used in this work (1,918 images for training). Since the training dataset used in this work has significantly fewer samples compared to the original training data on which these models are trained (ImageNet), we observed slight overfitting during the training process. In each deep architecture, all layers following the feature extraction layer were removed and replaced with global average pooling and dense layers. A neural network classifier is then introduced on top of the pooling layer, consisting of two fully connected (FC) layers with 256 and 128 neurons, followed by the *Softmax layer* with six neurons (correspond to six classes). The dense layer in the classification part was added to reduce the effect of over fitting. All models studied in this work are pretrained on the ImageNet dataset with 1K classes at the output layer and in this study, these models are trained on a downstream task with

Fig. 4: Fixed Feature Extraction (FFE) and Fine-Tuning (FT) are the two primary training schemes applied. Additionally, the CNN-based architectures were trained in Fixed Feature Extraction mode before Fine-Tuning (FFE + FT), which can enhance the performance of the fine-tuned model, as the pre-trained model initializes the weights in a more meaningful manner for Fine-Tuning.

Metric	Formula
Accuracy	$\frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN}$
Precision	$\frac{TP}{TP+FP}$
Recall	$\frac{TP}{TP+FN}$
F1-score	$2 * \frac{P * R}{P + R}$

TABLE III: Evaluation metrics for image classification.

only 6 classes of marine debris. Therefore, dense layers with *Dropout of 0.2* are added to reduce the size of feature maps. The training schemes applied in this study are presented in the following section.

B. Training schemes and Evaluation metrics

All CNNs based deep architectures were trained with three feature extraction schemes as illustrated in Fig. 4. *i) Fixed Feature Extraction (FFE)*: Freeze all its layers and train only classifier, *ii) Fine Tuning (FT)*: Fine-tune all the weights of the model and train it together with the classifier, *iii) Fixed Feature + Fine Tuning*: Initially, freeze the model for few epochs and train only the classifier, afterward unfreeze the last few layers (weights) to fine-tune. Training models with pre-trained weights can help the model to improve the generalization and proved to be an effective way in transfer learning. Training with fixed features for few epochs also help to initialize the weights of the model in a more meaningful manner, model will learn some relevant features before abrupt changes. All models were evaluated on the testing set using standard performance metrics: accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The mathematical formulation of these metrics is given in Table III, where TP represents true positive (correctly predicted positive instances), TN corresponds to true negative (correctly predicted negative instances), FP indicates false positive (negative instances mistakenly classified as positive), and FN represents false negative (positive instances incorrectly classified as negative). Additionally, P represents precision and R corresponds to

Model	Training	Val-Acc (%)	Precision (%)		Recall (%)		F1-score (%)	
			Macro	Weighted	Macro	Weighted	Macro	Weighted
VGG19	FFE	78.62	75.69	75.93	75.04	75.47	75.04	75.34
	FT	77.99	78.48	78.41	76.05	77.99	77.01	77.87
	FFE+FT	80.71	80.05	81.05	80.69	80.71	80.12	80.6
ResNet50	FFE	83.23	84.08	83.26	84.05	83.23	84.02	83.22
	FT	86.16	85.67	86.43	85.71	86.16	85.6	86.19
	FFE+FT	86.37	85.64	86.33	85.25	86.37	85.22	86.17
DenseNet121	FFE	84.28	84.68	84.46	85.01	84.28	84.71	84.21
	FT	85.74	85.44	85.78	84.19	85.74	84.7	85.63
	FFE+FT	90.99	92.31	91.11	90.77	90.99	91.46	91
InceptionV3	FFE	77.15	76.81	77.32	78.93	77.15	77.64	77.08
	FT	81.13	81.18	81.13	80.76	81.13	80.77	80.87
	FFE+FT	87.21	87.28	87.34	87.35	87.21	87.09	87.11
MobileNetV2	FFE	78.83	80.88	79.04	79.05	78.83	79.91	78.89
	FT	76.7	79.77	77.82	74.37	76.73	76.53	76.72
	FFE+FT	84.91	86.45	85.45	85.72	84.91	85.81	84.86
Inception-ResNetV2	FFE	82.6	85.46	82.92	81.75	82.6	83.35	82.61
	FT	89.94	91.38	90.02	90.21	89.94	90.68	89.9
	FFE+FT	89.73	89.48	89.78	90.14	89.73	89.74	89.69
Xception	FFE	78.2	80.15	78.13	77.82	78.2	78.82	78.03
	FT	85.95	86.54	86.85	84.28	85.95	85.05	86.12
	FFE+FT	88.47	90.39	89.85	91.02	89.73	90.53	89.62
NasNet	FFE	77.78	79.89	78.28	78.49	77.78	79.07	77.89
	FT	74.63	79.08	75.98	73.41	74.63	74.66	74.4
	FFE+FT	87	88.79	87.86	87.55	87	87.92	87.14
EfficientNetB0	FFE	81.97	82.52	79.26	78.05	78.83	79.69	78.53
	FT	83.44	84.76	83.9	81.74	83.44	82.88	83.37
	FFE+FT	85.12	86.08	85.67	84.98	85.12	85.14	85.11

TABLE IV: Evaluation of CNNs based architectures on test data across three different training schemes.

recall. While accuracy provides the ratio of correctly classified images to the total number of images in the dataset, it can be misleading in the context of an imbalanced dataset. Precision measures the ratio of correctly predicted positive data to all positive predictions. For class-wise evaluation, recall measures the ratio of correctly predicted positive measure of a specific class to all actual measures of that class. The F1-score indicates a balanced assessment of precision and recall. A higher F1-score reflects a better balance between precision and recall, a crucial aspect for accurate and reliable classification, particularly in the case of imbalanced datasets.

IV. RESULTS AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Table IV provides a comprehensive summary of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) across three different training schemes. Based on the comparative analysis, DenseNet121 exhibited robust performance across all training strategies, achieving the highest accuracy and F1-score. Overall, the DenseNet121 architecture, when trained with the combined training strategy (FFE+FT), achieved the highest accuracy of 90.99%, followed by Inception-ResNetV2

Fig. 5: Performance of three different training schemes on the test data in the form of box plots. Friedman test on the accuracy metrics (F-statistic=11.56, p-value=0.0031) indicates significant differences between the training schemes. Training the models with the combined training scheme (FFE + FT) consistently outperformed individual training schemes (FFE, FT) across all four metrics on test data.

and Xception when fine-tuned on the marine debris dataset. In general, training these models with the combination of FFE+FT proved to be effective, presenting significant improvements in all metrics. For example, DenseNet121 achieved an accuracy of 84.28% with the FFE training scheme. Further, FT and the combination of FFE+FT resulted in substantial accuracy improvements (90.99%) with more robust precision and recall metrics (91%). Among the models with fewer parameters, MobileNetV2 exhibited varying performance, with training using FE resulting in an accuracy of 78.83%. The combination of FFE and FT training further improved the performance, achieving an accuracy and F1-score of 84.91% and 84.86%, respectively.

Fig. 5 provides a comprehensive overview of the performance metrics for three training schemes (FFE, FT, and FFE + FT) across all CNN-based models trained on the marine debris dataset. The figure shows that training the models with the combined training scheme (FFE + FT) consistently outperformed individual training schemes (FFE, FT) in terms of all four metrics. Although fine-tuning leads to improvements in metrics compared to FFE, as explained earlier, training the models with fixed features for a few epochs can help to initialize the weights of the model in a significant manner. The model learns some relevant features before abrupt changes, crucially important if the new dataset significantly differs from the original pre-trained dataset (ImageNet). The selection of training schemes often depends on specific applications and tasks, such as the availability of computational resources *etc.*, but for the classification of underwater marine debris with a limited dataset, FFE+FT appeared to be the best training scheme for training purposes.

In the case of CNN-based models, we observed an overall significant improvement in the accuracy of the models when fine tuned. However, fine-tuning of ViT, DeiT, and Swin demonstrated limited improvement in the performances of the models. The ViT model achieved an accuracy of 88.90% with ImageNet weights, which increased to 89.10% when fine-tuned on the given dataset. Similarly, DeiT achieved an accuracy of 87.12% with ImageNet weights, which further increased to 88.47% when fine-tuned. Swin demonstrated the highest accuracy of 93.08% with fine-tuning, while the accuracy achieved by Swin with ImageNet weights is 92.54%. Fig. 6 summarizes the highest accuracies achieved by all the classification models investigated in this study, with the models listed in

Fig. 6: The accuracy achieved by CNNs and Transformers on test data.

order of decreasing accuracy. Among all the architectures trained on the given underwater marine debris dataset, Swin achieved the highest accuracy of 93.08%, followed by DenseNet121 (90.99%) and Inception-ResNetV2 (89.73%). Other top-performing models include DeiT (88.47%) and ViT (89.1%), also exhibiting competitive performance. However, VGG19 and MobileNetV2 achieved reasonable accuracies of 80.71% and 84.91%, respectively, the lowest among all.

Fig. 7 compares the overall performance of CNNs and transformer-based architectures for the classification of underwater marine debris. Both categories exhibited strong performance, but the provided data suggests that the transformer-based models achieved higher accuracies, with a median accuracy of 90.90%, compared to CNNs, which had a median accuracy of 87.49%, for the classification of underwater marine debris. We observed significant variation in the accuracy of CNN-based models, with some performing much better than others, accuracy ranging from 80.71% to 90.99%. This variation is mainly because CNNs are more sensitive to the choice of hyper-parameters and the type of data augmentation used during the training process. In contrast, the accuracies of transformer-based models are more consistent, ranging from 88.47% to 93.08%, as transformers utilize self-attention mechanisms to capture long-range dependencies across the entire image and are less sensitive to hyper-parameters and data augmentation.

Fig. 8 shows the performance of five different CNN and transformer-based classification models designed to reduce the number of parameters ($< 8M$), considering parameters counts and obtained accuracies. In general, models (DenseNet121, DeiT) with higher accuracies tend to have the most parameters, while models with the fewest parameters (MobileNetV2 and EfficientNetB0) also performed moderately, making them an efficient choice for certain deployment tasks. It is widely known that models with more parameters tend to be computationally expensive, and models with fewer parameters require fewer computational resources for training and deployment purposes. For deploying DL architecture on mobile or edge devices for the classification of underwater marine debris, based on the comparative analysis performed in this work, NasNet (Mobile) with a moderate parameter count provides a reasonable balance of accuracy and computational efficiency, trained on the dataset of underwater marine debris.

Fig. 7: Overall performance of CNNs and Transformer based architectures for the classification of underwater marine debris test data in the form of box plots. Transformer-based models achieved higher accuracies as compared to CNNs.

Fig. 8: Models complexity: Parameters vs Accuracy on test data. Deep architectures, such as DenseNet121 and DeiT, which achieve higher accuracies, generally have more parameters. On the other hand, models with fewer parameters, like MobileNetV2 and EfficientNetB0, exhibited moderate performance.

Fig. 9: Class-specific F1-scores of deep learning models. *Rubber* and *Glass* classes achieved the highest F1-scores, while the *Other* class obtained the lowest average score. DenseNet121 and Swin demonstrated the highest F1-scores among all classes.

Fig. 10: Normalized confusion matrices of the top-performing deep learning architectures (Swin Transformer, DenseNet121, and Inception-ResNetV2) alongside models with fewer parameters (DeiT, NasNet, and MobileNetV2 models).

Fig. 11: Illustration of inclass-variance: metal, plastic and other

Fig. 12: Illustration of accuracy, memory size and inference execution time of each model. The size of the bubble denotes the memory in MB of each model. Inference time of each model is computed on NVIDIA Tesla T4 (TU104) processor.

In Fig. 9, F1-scores of all models studied across different classes of marine debris are compared. Generally, all models achieved higher precision scores than recall, indicating more correct positive predictions. *Rubber* and *Glass* attained the highest precision and F1-scores, attributed to their distinct shape features and fewer in-class variations. DenseNet121 achieved the highest F1-score of 98.8% in predicting *Rubber*, while Xception achieved the highest F1-score of 95.77% to predict *Glass*. Overall, the *Other* obtained the lowest average F1-score of 85.54%, suggesting potential challenges in accurately classifying the diverse objects that lead to high in-class variations. Among CNNs based models, DenseNet121 consistently performed well across multiple trash classes, while other models excelled in specific categories. DenseNet121 achieved an average F1-score of 91.58%, followed by Xception (90.88%). Similarly, among the attention-based mechanisms, Swin transformer performed consistently well across all classes and achieved the highest average F1-score of 92.47%. Among all the models, VGG19 performed moderately across different classes, with relatively lower average F1-score of 79.75% as compared to the other models. In summary, models demonstrated diverse levels of effectiveness in classifying different classes, and the selection of the optimal model is associated with the specific priorities and requirements inherent to the classification task (*e.g.*, area, location). Therefore, this comparative analysis will help in identifying the model that performed best in classifying a specific category of marine debris. Fig. 10 presents the confusion matrices of the top-performing deep learning architectures (Swin transformer, DenseNet121, and Inception-ResNetV2) alongside models with fewer parameters (DeiT, NasNet, and MobileNetV2 models). The confusion matrices summarize the performance in identifying classes that are more challenging for a model to learn. For the classification of marine debris across all models, the *Other* trash class showed the most confusion, with corresponding images frequently misclassified as *Metal* or *Plastic*, and vice versa. Additionally, there were frequent instances where *Plastic* was mistaken for *Metal* and vice versa. Among all classes, the *Rubber* class demonstrated the most notable performance across all architectures due to its distinctive shape features. To summarize, the influence of imbalanced data on the outcome of the models was less evident,

as shown by the F1-Score and confusion matrices. However, as mentioned before, significant in-class variance was observed within the plastic and metal classes, as illustrated in Fig. 11. This variance occurs due to the similarity in shapes of *plastic* and *metal* objects across various training images (e.g., cylindrical/rectangular containers, plastic bags, disposable glasses). Similarly, the *other trash* class obtained the lowest average F1-score, suggesting potential challenges in accurately classifying the diverse objects that lead to high in-class variations. Conversely, the training data in the *Rubber* class, despite having a significantly lower number of training images (211), exhibited more robust performance. This performance can be attributed to the consistent shape and color (black/gray tires) of the objects within this class. The *Glass* category presented the significant challenges for all the models, primarily due to dynamic illuminations and the inherent transparent nature of the *Glass* category. Underwater environments, particularly at the seabed, exhibit dynamic lighting conditions, which can significantly impact the visual appearance of transparent objects, making them difficult for models to classify accurately. Furthermore, their transparent nature complicates the learning process for the deep architectures, as it presents difficulties in identifying clear visual boundaries. The lack of residual connections in VGG19 and EfficientNet could potentially contribute to the lower performance in the *Glass* category. Additionally, the pre-trained ImageNet dataset, used for initializing the weights of the models, contains relatively fewer transparent objects compared to other. This limited representation of transparent objects in the pre-training data might hinder the ability to generalize effectively to unseen samples of transparent objects during transfer learning. Table V provides an overview of the results achieved by various methods in the literature for the classification of underwater marine debris. These methods employ different deep architectures and utilize diverse datasets for training purposes. Additionally, the evaluation parameters used to report their performance in detecting or classifying underwater marine debris vary. We have summarized these methods in the table in terms of dataset, evaluation metrics, and network architecture.

Inference time and memory consumption are crucial factors in assessing the performance of deep architectures for real time application. Most importantly, for the edge devices with limited computational resources, inference time and memory consumption are two extremely important constrained by the hardware on which the model is deployed. Fig. 12, illustrated the overview of the memory size, inference execution time, and accuracy of each model for the given underwater marine dataset. For the given scenario, VGG19 exhibited the highest latency with the execution time of 633ms, whereas MobileNet particularly designed for edge devices performed most efficiently. In this section, we have presented the performance and comparative analysis of CNNs and transformer-based architectures as feature extractors for classifying underwater marine debris images. We employed three different training schemes to highlight the most optimal training criteria. Based on the obtained results, the combined training strategy (FFE+FT), where we initially freeze the weights of the model for a few epochs and train only the classifier, afterward unfreezing the last few layers (weights) to fine-tune, proved to be most effective. Transformer-based models achieved relatively higher accuracies compared to CNNs. Swin achieved the highest accuracy but at the cost of a higher number of parameters, followed closely by DenseNet121, which has three times fewer parameters. Among transformer-based models, DeiT achieved an accuracy of 88.47% with a number of parameters (5.53M) less than DenseNet121. MobileNetV2, with the fewest parameters at 2.26M, achieved an accuracy of 84.91%.

Author	Target Domain	Architecture	Dataset	Results
Corrigan et al. [15]	Ocean plastic	YOLOACT	TrashCAN	mAP = 0.365
		Mask R-CNN		mAP = 0.377
Sanjai et al. [5]	Pollution (Low/Medium/Clean)	Inception-ResNet V2	Google based Images	Accuracy = 96.4
		InceptionV3		
Music et al. [12]	Cardboard, Glass, Paper, Metal, Plastic	VGG16	Hybrid dataset	Accuracy = 85
		YOLO V3		Recall = 43.0 Precision = 71.0 Accuracy = 36.0
Ferrer et al. [13]	Glass, Metal, Plastic, wood, Other	Mask R-CNN	JEDI dataset	mAP = 65.2

TABLE V: Comparison of the performance of approaches to detection and classification of marine debris.

V. CONCLUSION

Underwater marine debris classification plays a vital role in understanding the extent, sources, and impacts of marine pollution. Accurate classification of these items is crucial for developing effective strategies to reduce further addition and protect the health of marine ecosystems. However, classifying underwater marine debris is a challenging task with several limitations. Deep learning methods enable end-to-end learning, allowing models to learn hierarchical representations directly from input data, eliminating the need for manual feature extraction. However, training deep learning models requires a large amount of data, and acquiring diverse and substantial underwater marine debris data has its limitations, as explained before. In this study, the type-specific marine debris data set collected from the deep sea is utilized to train all deep architectures. The data set is mainly categorized by the shapes and type of materials of the objects and most prominent among them is glass, metal, plastic and rubber. The main contribution of this work is to utilize transfer learning across various deep architectures, such as CNNs and transformers, to assess their performance when trained on an underwater marine debris dataset. Among the six classes of marine debris studied in this work, rubber and glass exhibited the highest precision and F1-scores, due to their distinctive shape features and fewer variations within their respective classes. Moreover, there was frequent mis-classification between metal and plastic classes, where plastic was often mistakenly identified as metal, and vice versa, due to shared visual characteristics and complexities in their appearances. The Swin transformer and DenseNet121 demonstrated the highest overall accuracy. DeiT achieved an accuracy of 88.47% with a relatively lower parameter count compared to DenseNet121. MobileNetV2, designed specifically for edge devices with the fewest parameters (2.26M), achieved an accuracy of 84.91% in classifying underwater marine debris. Though the training of all the models is performed on a real underwater marine debris dataset, the main limitation of this study is the training of models on a limited dataset. Since we performed transfer learning and most of the deep architectures trained on ImageNet datasets are complex and differ significantly from the problem considered in this work, we observed high variance during training, which leads to over fitting. Therefore, further domain-specific fine-tuning and optimization techniques can help to improve performance using the transfer learning approach. We conclude that the choice between CNNs and transformers depends on factors such as data availability, computational resources, and specific conditions of underwater environments. While selecting the deep architecture,

Careful consideration of these elements ensures the best performance for the unique demands of underwater debris classification. As artificial intelligence-based technologies advance, the focus will shift towards developing end-to-end models capable of real-time underwater marine pollution monitoring directly on edge devices. The study performed in this work assists in selecting the best model suited for given computational resources, ensuring model efficiency and adaptability in dynamic underwater conditions. The future extension of this study is to perform model optimization using pruning and quantization-based techniques to further optimize these models while maintaining performance in the given dynamic environment. Additionally, considering the vast monitoring area and the need for efficient monitoring, decentralized model training of deep neural architectures for detecting underwater marine debris could be an effective approach to explore in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This study has been funded in part by PON “Ricerca –Innovazione” 2014-2020 and by the project CLEVER (Project ID 101097560), that is supported by the Key Digital Technologies Joint Undertaking and its members (including top-up funding by Italian Ministry of University and Research — MUR).

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Madricardo et al. “How to Deal With Seafloor Marine Litter: An Overview of the State-of-the-Art and Future Perspectives”, *Frontiers in Marine Science*, Marine Pollution, 7, 30, Sept 2020.
- [2] M. Taye et al., “Understanding of Machine Learning with Deep Learning: Architectures, Workflow, Applications and Future Directions”, *Computers*, 5, 91, Dec 2023.
- [3] I. Marin et al., “Deep-Feature-Based Approach to Marine Debris Classification”, *Applied Science*, 5644, Nov 2021.
- [4] M. Paula et al., “Assessment of marine litter through remote sensing: recent approaches and future goals”, *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 168, 112347, 2021.
- [5] P. Sanjai et al., “Ocean litter detection using inception transfer learning models”, *Defense + Commercial Sensing*, June 2023.
- [6] K. Kyllili et al., “An intelligent way for discerning plastics at the shorelines and the seas”, *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27, 34:42631-42643, Dec 2020.
- [7] M. Hidaka et al., “Pixel-level image classification for detecting beach litter using a deep learning approach”, *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 175, 113371, Feb 2022.
- [8] C. Martin et al., “Use of unmanned aerial vehicles for efficient beach litter monitoring”, *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 131, 662–673, June 2018.
- [9] A. Papakonstantinou et al., “A Citizen Science Unmanned Aerial System Data Acquisition Protocol and Deep Learning Techniques for the Automatic Detection and Mapping of Marine Litter Concentrations in the Coastal Zone”, *Drones*, 5, 6, Jan 2021.
- [10] G. Goncalves et al., “Mapping marine litter using UAS on a beach-dune system: A multidisciplinary approach” *The Science of the Total Environment*, 706, 135742, Nov 2019.
- [11] M. Fulton et al., “Robotic Detection of Marine Litter Using Deep Visual Detection Models”, *International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Montreal, QC, Canada, pp. 5752-5758, May 2019.
- [12] J. Music et al., “Detecting Underwater Sea Litter Using Deep Neural Networks: An Initial Study” *International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies*, Croatia, pp. 1-6, 2020.
- [13] S. Ferrer et al. “An experimental study on marine debris location and recognition using object detection”, *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 168, 154-161, April 2023.
- [14] D. Politikos et al. “Automatic detection of seafloor marine litter using towed camera images and deep learning”, *Marine pollution bulletin*, 164, 111974, March 2021.
- [15] B. Corrigan et al., “Real-Time Instance Segmentation for Detection of Underwater Litter as a Plastic Source”, *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 11, 8, 1532, July 2023.

- [16] B. Jalil et al. "Comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms for the classification of underwater marine debris", *2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for the Sea; Learning to Measure Sea Health Parameters*, 2, 116-120, 2023.
- [17] JAMSTEC, <https://www.godac.jamstec.go.jp/bismal/e/dataset/JAMSTEC>
- [18] J. Gu et al., "Recent advances in convolutional neural networks", *Pattern Recognition*, 77, 354–377, May 2018.
- [19] K. Simonyan et al., "Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition", *3rd International Conference on Learning Representations*, 1–14, 2015.
- [20] C. Szegedy et al., "Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision", *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, USA, 2818-2826, 2016.
- [21] H. Kaiming et al. "Deep Residual Learning for Image Recognition", *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 770-778, 2016.
- [22] C. Szegedy et al., "Inception-v4, inception-ResNet and the impact of residual connections on learning", *Thirty-First AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, AAAI Press, 4278–4284, Feb 2017.
- [23] C. Francois, "Xception: Deep Learning with Depthwise Separable Convolutions", *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 1800-1807, 2017.
- [24] G. Huang et al., "Densely Connected Convolutional Networks", *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 4700-4708, 2017.
- [25] Sandler, Mark et al., "MobileNetV2: Inverted Residuals and Linear Bottlenecks", *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 4510-4520, 2018.
- [26] B. Zoph et al., "Learning Transferable Architectures for Scalable Image Recognition", *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 8697-8710, 2018.
- [27] M. Tan et al., "EfficientNet: Rethinking Model Scaling for Convolutional Neural Networks," *36th International Conference on Machine Learning*, 6105–6114, 2019.
- [28] Vaswani et al., "Attention is all you need" , *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 30, 2017.
- [29] S. Khan et al., "Transformers in Vision: A Survey", *ACM Computing survey*, 54, 10, 41, Jan 2022.
- [30] A. Dosovitskiy et al., "An Image Is Worth 16x16 Words: Transformers for Image Recognition at Scale", *Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2020.
- [31] T. Hugo et al. "Training data-efficient image transformers and distillation through attention", *International Conference on Machine Learning*, 2020.
- [32] Z. Liu, et al., "Swin Transformer: Hierarchical Vision Transformer using Shifted Windows," *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision*, Montreal, Canada, 9992-10002, 2021.
- [33] Deng, J. et al., ImageNet: A Large-Scale Hierarchical Image Database. *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2009.

Bushra Jalil received Erasmus Mundus Master degree in Computer Vision and Robotics in 2008. She received PhD in non-linear signal analysis for medical applications from Université de Bourgogne, France in 2011. She has worked as a research fellow in the Signal and Images laboratory of the Institute of Information Science and Technologies 'Alessandro Faedo' in Pisa. Since 2022, she has been an Assistant professor at the TeCIP institute of Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna in Pisa, Italy. Her research interest includes artificial intelligence, computer vision, infrared and thermal imaging, biomedical imaging and data fusion algorithms.

Luca Maggiani received the Ph.D. degree from Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Pisa, and Université Clermont Auvergne, Clermont Ferrand, in 2017. He is the Co-Founder and the CEO of SmaRTy SAS, and CEO of Sma-RTy Italia SRL. He manages a Research and Development Team for advanced artificial intelligence applications and at the same time, develops computer vision application for automotive and surveillance. During his research activity, he has coauthored over 15 international reviews on embedded smart video sensors, bio-inspired systems and their processing architectures.

Luca Valcarengi has been an Associate Professor at Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, Pisa, Italy, since 2014. He has published more than 300 papers in international journals and conference proceedings and actively participated in the TPC of several IEEE conferences, such as GLOBECOM and ICC. His research interests include optical networks design, analysis, optimization, artificial intelligence optimization techniques, communication networks reliability, fixed and mobile network integration, fixed network backhauling for mobile networks, and energy efficiency in communications networks. He received a Fulbright Research Scholar Fellowship, in 2009, and a JSPS “Invitation Fellowship Program for Research in Japan (Long Term),” in 2013.